

Finite bending of non-slender beams and the limitations of the *Elastica* theory

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Abstract

The problem of slender solids under finite bending has been addressed recently in [1]. Here, such a model is extended to short solids by improving the background formulation. In particular, the model is refined by imposing the vanishing of the axial force over the cross sections. The geometrical *neutral loci*, corresponding to unstretched and unstressed surfaces, are identified in closed form and discussed. It is shown that approximations of the model can lead to significant values of the axial stress resultants despite the pure bending conditions.

For a generic form of compressible stored energy function, a nonlinear moment-curvature relation accounting for both material and geometric nonlinearities is provided and then specialized for a compressible Mooney-Rivlin material. A proper normalisation of the moment-curvature relation highlights the role played by the *Eulerian slenderness* of the solid, putting in light the limitations of the *Elastica*. The obtained results are compared with FE simulations providing excellent agreement.

Keywords: Pure bending, moment-curvature relation, finite elasticity, *Elastica* theory, neutral loci.

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1. Introduction

The theory of finite bending plays a basic role in various everyday applications. The mechanical response of a variety of structures as electro-mechanical components [2, 3], biological tissues [4], or plants and animals [5] can be assessed through the theory of bending.

In the framework of linearised elasticity based on small displacements and infinitesimal deformations, the theory of bending was handled in the pioneering works by Bernoulli [6, 7], Euler [8, 9, 10], and Navier [11, 12]. Nonetheless, the linearised formulations turn out to be inadequate for systems subjected to large bending. This occurs even more for cases where materials exhibit strong geometric or constitutive nonlinearities. As an example, constitutive nonlinearities play a pivotal role in the frameworks of plasticity, viscoelasticity or phase changes, in which multi-linear [13, 14] or more complex [15] models may be used properly.

When beams subjected to bending are characterised by large displacements but small deformations, the *Euler Elastica* (EE) can be adequate. Such a formulation has been widely used to address displacements [16, 17, 18], interaction problems [19] and loss of stability [20, 21]. Only few studies handle the EE formulation coupled with a nonlinear constitutive law. A noteworthy approach to investigate systems under large displacements consists in the use of elastic beam-like elements, modelled through the EE formulation, combined with lumped translational or rotational springs [22]. As pointed out in [23, 1, 22], there is a lack of kinematic models to accounting for the transverse kinematics of the cross section with the longitudinal behaviour of the solid. Indeed, most of the existing theoretical models assume plane strain or plane stress conditions. In this respect, the approach proposed in [23] is noteworthy as it couples the longitudinal finite deformation with the kinematics of the cross sections based on linearised theory of plates.

As known, the (fully nonlinear) context of finite elasticity removes any assumption about the smallness of the displacements and deformations and the

linearity of the constitutive law as well. Theory of bending was extended to the framework of finite deformations by Rivlin [24] by assuming plane strain assumption. Based on the Rivlin work, over time many models have been proposed in the Literature to date. The finite bending of a rectangular block made of Hencky material was investigated in [25], whereas in [26] finite bending of rectangular block was extended to a general hyperelastic incompressible material. The electroelastic behavior of a layered elastomer actuator was investigated in [27] under plane deformation conditions. The effect of the form of the stored energy functions on the moment-curvature relationship has been studied in [28]. Based on finite elasticity, bending theory has been used to investigate instability in [29, 30]. However, all the aforementioned works have been performed making reference to plane strain condition and/or nearly incompressibility assumption.

The 3D model for finite theory of bent solids [1] was extended to the case of slender solids in [31, 32, 33], and later extended to viscous materials in [34].

Also numerical formulations and experimental tests aimed at simulating the effects induced by pure bending loadings can be found in Literature. A numerical solution of the bending problem in a 3D layout based on variational formulation was proposed in [35, 36] for a hyperelastic materials. Many experimental devices and tests have been proposed in the Literature to induce pure flexion without inducing axial or shear forces [28, 37, 38, 39].

In the present study, conversely to [1], equilibrium conditions are made more robust by imposing the vanishing of the axial force over the cross sections. Expressions of *neutral loci* corresponding to unstretched and unstressed surfaces of the bent solid are provided in closed form. Linearisations of the proposed model are provided leading to two approximated solutions: the EE and the *nonlinear Euler Elastica* (NEE) formulations. A new moment-curvature relationship is provided accounting for both transversal and longitudinal deformations of the solid. Summing up, the aims of the present work are the following:

- improving the 3D model of finite bending of prismatic hyperelastic and compressible solids proposed recently in [1];

- providing closed form expressions for the relevant neutral loci of a bent solid;
- highlighting the nonlinear nature of the bending moment vs *Eulerian slenderness* through a proper normalized relationship valid for any aspect ratio of the bent solid;
- discussing the limitations of the EE formulation together with the limits in using the new proposed theory of bending.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, analytic preliminaries concerning both the kinematics and statics of the theoretical formulation are presented. The kinematics of the problem has been described thoroughly in [1]. Nonetheless, assumptions and governing kinematic parameters are briefly recalled in Section 2.1. The resume of the kinematics and resumed in Appendix A for convenience. Appendix B describes the neutral loci of both kinematics and mechanics of the present bending model of solids. The new mechanical model is presented in Section 2.2 by discussing the main differences with respect to [1] and supporting the importance of the new equilibrium conditions. The general bending moment-curvature relation is obtained in Section 3 and then specialised in Section 4 for a compressible Mooney-Rivlin (MR) material. Section 5 introduces the FE model whose results are compared with respect to present model and other formulations in Section 6. Finally, conclusion are drawn in Section 7.

2. Analytic preliminaries

The present Section deals with the kinematics and the mechanical model. It is remarked that the kinematic model describes the three-dimensional deformation field affecting the solid, accounting for the anticlastic effect arising in the planes of the cross sections, as hereinafter elucidated.

2.1. Kinematic model

A prismatic solid¹ of length L and rectangular cross section $B \times H$ is considered according to Figure 1. Reference is made to a Cartesian coordinate

Figure 1: Prismatic solid subjected to finite bending: reference system $\{O, X, Y, Z\}$, reference configuration (grey solid) and deformed configuration (black solid).

system $\{O, X, Y, Z\}$ with the origin placed at the centroid of the solid. The solid is made of a hyperelastic, homogeneous and isotropic material. Each point $P \equiv (X, Y, Z)$, belonging to the reference configuration of the solid, is identified by the position vector $\mathbf{id}(P) = X\hat{\mathbf{i}} + Y\hat{\mathbf{j}} + Z\hat{\mathbf{k}}$, being $\hat{\mathbf{i}}$, $\hat{\mathbf{j}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ the unit vectors of the Cartesian axes. The displacement vector $\mathbf{sp}(P) = u(P)\hat{\mathbf{i}} + v(P)\hat{\mathbf{j}} + w(P)\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ (given in Table A.1) moves the point P to the deformed configuration $P' \equiv (x(P), y(P), z(P))$. The deformation vector $\boldsymbol{\varphi}(P) = x\hat{\mathbf{i}} + y\hat{\mathbf{j}} + z\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ identifies the point P' in the deformed configuration according to the map $\boldsymbol{\varphi}(P) = \mathbf{id}(P) + \mathbf{sp}(P)$, see Figure 1.

As depicted in Figure 2, due to the prescribed rotation α_0 of the final cross sections of the body, the solid is bent in such way to deform by according to

¹The term *solid* will be used in the following to remark the difference with respect to the term *beam* or *rod*, which are typically considered in framework of linearised elasticity or EE formulation. In particular, a beam or rod are a slender 3D elements whilst the solid is here assumed as non-slender 3D element without restrictions in terms of geometries.

Figure 2: Kinematic model of a prismatic solid subjected to finite bending: (a) kinematics in the longitudinal ZY plane at $X = 0$; (b) detail about the unstretched fibers QN and QM and principal stretch distributions along the Y axis; (c) kinematics in the transverse $X\tilde{Y}$ planes.

three main kinematic assumptions [1]: in the ZY planes the longitudinal radii of curvature are constants along the Z axis; cross sections of the solid remain plane after deformation; all the cross sections deform in the same way into sectors of a circular crown.

The displacement field is characterized by three kinematic unknowns that are determined by imposing equilibrium conditions. The Y coordinate of the unstretched fiber lying in the planes of the cross sections is denoted by QN and it is one of the unknowns of the problem. The transverse principal stretches, $\lambda_1(P)$ and $\lambda_2(P)$, turn out to be [1]

$$\lambda_1(Y) = \lambda_2(Y) = \lambda(Y) = \frac{r_O}{r} e^{-\frac{Y}{r}}, \quad (1)$$

being r_O the transverse radius of curvature associated to the centroid of the solid (see Table A.1) and r denotes the anticlastic radius of curvature associated to

the *transverse neutral fiber* $N \equiv (0, -QN, Z)^2$. It follows that $\lambda(N) = 1$, see Figure 2. The anticlastic radius of curvature r is the second unknowns of the problem.

Along the Z direction, the fiber N is characterized by the longitudinal radius of curvature R that is the third unknown of the problem. An important role is played by the kinematic parameter QM (see eq.(B.1)) that denotes the Y coordinate corresponding to the longitudinal fiber lying in the YZ plane that preserves its length after deformation. Such a fiber is $M \equiv (0, -QM, Z)$ and it represents the *longitudinal neutral fiber* for which $\lambda_3(M) = 1$, being λ_3 the longitudinal principal stretch, which reads

$$\lambda_3(X, Y) = \frac{R+r}{R_0} - \frac{r_0}{R_0} e^{-\frac{Y}{r}} \cos \beta, \quad (2)$$

being $\beta = X/r$. Final cross sections of the solid at $Z = \pm L/2$ and lateral surfaces of the solid at $X = \pm B/2$ rotate by the angles $2\alpha_0 = L/R_0$ and $2\beta_0 = B/r$, respectively, being R_0 the longitudinal radius of curvature associated to the fiber M , as depicted in Figure 2³. Therefore, the kinematic parameter quantifying the flexure acting on the system is α_0 or, equivalently, R_0 .

2.2. Mechanic model

The first Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor \mathbf{T}_R is given in terms of the constitutive law as

$$\mathbf{T}_R = \frac{\partial W}{\partial \mathbf{F}} = 2 \left[(W_{,1} + I_1 W_{,2}) \mathbf{F} - W_{,2} \mathbf{B} \mathbf{F}^T + I_3 W_{,3} \mathbf{F}^{-T} \right], \quad (3)$$

in which \mathbf{F} is the deformation gradient, $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{F} \mathbf{F}^T$ is the left Cauchy deformation tensor, and $W_{,i} = \partial W / \partial I_i$ denotes derivatives of the stored energy density function $W(I_1, I_2, I_3)$ with respect to the deformation invariants I_i , with $i = 1, 2, 3$.

²For the details about the neutral fibers see Appendix B.

³It is remarked that both QM and QN are quantities defined in the reference configuration. In deformed configuration it follows $y(N) - y(M) = R_0 - R$. Conversely to the present formulation, in the beam model proposed in [31, 32] one has $QN = QM = 0$ and $R = R_0$.

The governing quantities of the mechanic model turn out to be the principal components of the Biot stress tensor, $\mathbf{T}_B = \mathbf{R}^{-1}\mathbf{T}_R$ [40], as reported in Table A.2. In particular, for the problem at hand, the Biot principal stresses assume the following form:

$$T_{B_1}(P) = 2\frac{r_O}{r^3}e^{-\frac{3Y}{r}} \left\{ r^2 e^{\frac{2Y}{r}} \left\{ W_{,1} + W_{,2} \left[\left(\frac{R+r-r_O e^{-\frac{Y}{r}} \cos \beta}{R_0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{r_O}{r} e^{-\frac{Y}{r}} \right)^2 \right] \right\} + W_{,3} \left(r_O \frac{R+r-r_O e^{-\frac{Y}{r}} \cos \beta}{R_0} \right)^2 \right\}, \quad (4)$$

$$T_{B_3}(P) = \frac{2e^{-\frac{5Y}{r}} \left[(r+R)e^{\frac{Y}{r}} - r_O \cos \beta \right]}{r^4 R_0} \left[\left(r e^{\frac{Y}{r}} \right)^4 W_{,1} + 2 \left(r r_O e^{\frac{Y}{r}} \right)^2 W_{,2} + r_O^4 W_{,3} \right]. \quad (5)$$

Note that T_{B_2} corresponds with T_{B_1} as a consequence of the main assumptions of the model. Similarly to the principal stretches (1) and (2), also the principal stresses (4) and (5) are even functions of the X coordinate. Both principal stretches and stresses do not depend on the Z coordinate because of the uniform bending.

As thoroughly investigated in [1], a nonlinear system of three equations is achieved by imposing the equilibrium conditions. The solution of this nonlinear system provides the kinematic unknowns R , r , and QN .

The first equation of the nonlinear system involves the material divergence of the stress tensor \mathbf{T}_R . Making reference to the transverse neutral fiber N , under the assumption of zero body forces, it was shown in [1] that the indefinite equilibrium equations reduce to

$$\frac{T_{B_1}}{r} = \frac{T_{B_3}}{R_0}, \quad \text{for } N \equiv (0, -QN, Z), \quad (6)$$

which, in terms of the stored energy function, turns out to be

$$\begin{aligned} & W_{,1} + W_{,2} \frac{2R_0^2}{rR} + W_{,3} \left(\frac{2R}{r} - 1 \right) + W_{,11} \left(\frac{4R_0^2}{rR} - 2 \right) + 2W_{,12} \left(\frac{4R_0^2 + 2R^2}{Rr} - \right. \\ & \left. \frac{R^2}{R_0^2} - 2 \right) + W_{,13} \left(\frac{8R}{r} - \frac{2R^2}{R_0^2} - 2 \right) - W_{,22} \frac{2(R^2 + R_0^2)(rR - 2R_0^2)}{rRR_0^2} + \\ & 2W_{,23} \left[\frac{2R(2R_0^2 - rR + R^2)}{rR_0^2} - 1 \right] - W_{,33} \frac{2R^2(r - 2R)}{rR_0^2} = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The equilibrium equations at the free surfaces of the solid are fulfilled by imposing vanishing circuitry of the Piola-Kirchhoff stress vector $\mathbf{t}_R = \mathbf{T}_R \mathbf{n}$, being \mathbf{n} the unit normal at the boundaries of the body. By imposing such a condition one has

$$\oint_{\mathcal{L}} \mathbf{t}_R d\mathcal{L} = \int_{-H/2}^{+H/2} T_{B_1}(B/2, Y) dY - [o(QN/r) + o(H/r)] = 0. \quad (8)$$

Conversely to [1], the last equation required for the solution of the problem is the vanishing of the axial force N over the cross sections⁴, namely

$$N = \int_A T_{B_3}(X, Y) dA = 0. \quad (9)$$

It will be shown that condition (9), that was not considered in [1], significantly increases the accuracy of theoretical model for prediction of stretches and stresses also for very short solids under extremely large deformations. Thereby, the problem of flexure of solids is handled by solving numerically the coupled system of nonlinear eqns.(7), (8), and (9) in the kinematic unknowns R, r , and QN .

Let us discuss about the nonlinear distribution of the stress component $T_{B_3}(0, Y)$ along the Y axis in order to show the relevance of eq.(9). The non-linearity of the stress distribution within the height of the solid increases as the rotation angle α_0 increases, as sketched qualitatively in Figure 3(a). Such a figure highlights the *partialization* of the cross section: upper portion of the solid is subjected to tension whereas lower portion is prone to compression.

As known, the most part of materials under moderate deformations are characterised by a uniaxial stress-stretch curve ($T_{R_{33}}$ vs λ_3) that exhibits softening

⁴In the initial version [1] of the present model, eq.(9) was not considered. A geometrical consideration about the *almost linearity* of the transversal principal stretch distribution was assumed leading to the following condition:

$$\frac{1}{2} \left[e^{-\frac{1}{r}(QN + \frac{H}{2})} + e^{-\frac{1}{r}(QN - \frac{H}{2})} \right] \cong 1.$$

Such an assumption leads to accurate predictions only for moderate deformations and solids with compact cross sections.

Figure 3: Distribution of the longitudinal stress $T_{B_3}(X, Y)$: (a) evolution of the stress distribution at $X = 0$ and motion of the unstressed fiber QM_R as the prescribed rotation α_0 increases; (b) stress distribution at $X = 0$ in case of balance between compressive and tensile longitudinal stress resultants (solid line), nonlinear unbalanced stress distribution (dotted line), and linear balanced stress distribution (dashed line).

under tension and hardening under compression. It follows that the balance of normal tractions over the cross section can be fulfilled only if the unstressed fiber (QM_R in Figure 3) moves toward the bottom of the cross section as the deformation increases⁵. This is the only way to ensure the balance between the resultant of normal traction inside the compressed region (N_c in Figure 3(b)) and resultant of normal traction of region under tension (N_t). If the unstressed fiber is assumed *a priori* at $Y = 0$, the nonlinear (and monotonic) stress distribution turns out to be unbalanced, as sketched by the dotted curve in Figure 3(b) for $X = 0$.⁶ Note also that the dependence on the X coordinate of the stress distribution is introduced by the principal stretches (1) and (2) through the term $\cos(X/r)$. Due to the smallness of the term X/r , it follows that normal tractions along Y coordinate do not change relevantly varying X . Such a variation becomes relevant as the width of the solid increases with respect to the height, namely for great values of the compactness index $\beta_C = B/H$. For solids

⁵The considerations regarding the stress distribution across the height of the cross section (see also Section 4.3) are relevant in order to explain the unbalanced stress profile provided by the nonlinear Euler *Elastica* formulation.

⁶It is remarked that a compressive behaviour in hardening and tensile behaviour in softening with monotonic trend has been assumed.

with large values of β_C , the coordinates QM_R can also be placed at $Y > 0$ (see Figure B.13).

Relation $\mathbf{id}(P) = \boldsymbol{\varphi}(P) - \mathbf{sp}(P)$ provides Eulerian coordinates x, y , and z as a function of Lagrangian coordinates X, Y and Z (see Table A.1). Moreover, based on the first Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor \mathbf{T}_R (3), the Cauchy stress tensor $\mathbf{T}(P')$ follows from the well known relation $\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{T}_R \mathbf{F}^T / \det(\mathbf{F})$. In particular, in the principal reference system, Cauchy stress tensor assumes the following diagonal form:

$$[\mathbf{T}] = \begin{bmatrix} T_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & T_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & T_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{T_{B_1}}{\lambda\lambda_3} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{T_{B_1}}{\lambda\lambda_3} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{T_{B_3}}{\lambda^2} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (10)$$

or equivalently in terms of Cauchy principal stress components

$$T_i = \frac{T_{B_i}}{\lambda_i} \left(\frac{\delta_{i1}}{\lambda_3} + \frac{\delta_{i3}}{\lambda_i} \right) \quad (\text{no summation}),$$

being δ_{ij} the Kronecker symbol ($i = 1$ and 3)⁷. In (10), the principal stretches λ_i are given in terms of Eulerian coordinates as

$$\lambda(P') = \sqrt{\frac{x^2 + \left[R + r - \sqrt{z^2 + (y + R + r - r_O)^2} \right]^2}{r^2}}, \quad (11)$$

$$\lambda_3(P') = \sqrt{\frac{z^2 + (y + R + r - r_O)^2}{R_0^2}}. \quad (12)$$

In the next Section, based on the above expressions, bending moment-curvature relation will be obtained.

3. Bending moment-curvature relation of a bent solids

The relations about the kinematics and the mechanical model reported above are used in the following to evaluate the moment-curvature relationship of a

⁷At $Z = 0$ principal directions of Cauchy stress tensor correspond to the Cartesian axes XYZ . Observing the stress component T_3 in eq.(10), it follows that Biot stress component T_{B_3} governs the position of the unstressed fiber in both reference and deformed configuration (as discussed in Appendix B).

uniformly bent hyperelastic solid.

The bending moment is evaluated making reference to the deformed configuration of the cross section. Therefore, based on the Cauchy stress component T_3 given in eq.(10), the moment-curvature relation reads⁸

$$m_x(R_0) = \int_{A'} \hat{y}(P') T_3(P') dA', \quad (13)$$

being $\hat{y} = \tilde{y}_P - \tilde{y}_M$ the arm of the Cauchy stress T_3 with respect to the longitudinal unstretched fiber and A' the deformed cross section area. Making reference

Figure 4: Deformed configuration of a generic cross section: polar reference system $\{C, \rho, \beta\}$ for the evaluation of the bending moment with longitudinal fibers (elongated in the upper part and contracted in the lower part).

to the polar reference system $\{C, \rho, \beta\}$ of Figure 4, Eulerian principal stretches

⁸It is recalled that the problem at hand accounts for uniform bending, thus the bending moment does not depend on the Z coordinate ($Z = z = 0$ can be assumed to handle formula (13)).

(11) and (12), Cauchy stress component T_3 , and its arm turn out to be

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda(\rho, \beta) &= \sqrt{\frac{(\rho \sin \beta)^2 + (\rho \cos \beta - r + r_O)^2}{r^2}}, \quad \lambda_3(\rho, \beta) = \frac{R + 2r - r_O - \rho \cos \beta}{R_0}, \\ T_3(\rho, \beta) &= \frac{2(\rho \cos \beta - 2r - R + r_O)}{r^2 R_0 [\rho^2 \sin^2 \beta + (\rho \cos \beta - 3r - 2R + r_O)^2]} \left\{ r^4 W_{,1} + 2r^2 [\rho^2 \sin^2 \beta + \right. \\ &\quad \left. (\rho \cos \beta - r + r_O)^2] W_{,2} + [\rho^2 \sin^2 \beta + (\rho \cos \beta - r + r_O)^2]^2 W_{,3} \right\}, \quad (14) \\ \hat{y}(\rho, \beta) &= r - \rho \cos \beta - (R_0 - R). \quad (15)\end{aligned}$$

Thus, the introduction of relations (14) and (15) into (13) provides the most general form of the nonlinear moment-curvature relation as

$$\begin{aligned}m_x(R_0) &= 4 \int_0^{\beta_0} \int_{r_{\min}}^{r_{\max}} \frac{\rho(r + R - R_0 - \rho \cos \beta)(\rho \cos \beta - 2r - R + r_O)}{r^2 R_0 [\rho^2 \sin^2 \beta + (\rho \cos \beta - 3r - 2R + r_O)^2]} \times \\ &\quad \left\{ r^4 W_{,1} + 2r^2 [\rho^2 \sin^2 \beta + (\rho \cos \beta - r + r_O)^2] W_{,2} + \right. \\ &\quad \left. [\rho^2 \sin^2 \beta + (\rho \cos \beta - r + r_O)^2]^2 W_{,3} \right\} d\rho d\beta, \quad (16)\end{aligned}$$

being r_{\min} and r_{\max} the minimum and maximum anticlastic radii of curvature of the fibers at $Y = \pm H/2$ respectively (see Table A.1).

Conversely to the *Elastica*, the moment-curvature relation (16) is coupled with the kinematic unknowns QN, r , and R provided by the solution of the nonlinear system of eqns. (7), (8) and (9).

4. Application to a compressible Mooney-Rivlin material

In the present section, the proper expression of the stored energy density function $W(I_1, I_2, I_3)$ for a compressible Mooney-Rivlin (MR) material is provided. Then, the mechanical model and, in turn, moment-curvature relationship are specialised according to it. Finally, approximations of the present theory are introduced, thus leading to the nonlinear Euler *Elastica* and Euler *Elastica* theories.

4.1. Stored energy function

Let us consider a compressible Mooney-Rivlin (MR) material characterized by the stored energy density function [41]

$$W(I_1, I_2, I_3) = aI_1 + bI_2 + \Gamma(I_3) + \omega_0, \quad a > 0, b > 0, \omega_0 \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (17)$$

in which $\Gamma :]0, +\infty[\rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a polyconvex function satisfying $\Gamma(I_3) \xrightarrow{I_3 \rightarrow 0^+} +\infty$ that introduces the dependence on the third invariant of deformation as [42]

$$\Gamma(I_3) = cI_3 - \frac{d}{2} \log(I_3), \quad c > 0, d > 0. \quad (18)$$

Constants d and ω_0 in (17) and (18) follow from the conditions of vanishing energy and absence of traction when $\lambda = \lambda_3 = 1$, as shown in [43]. These conditions lead to

$$\begin{cases} \omega_0 = -3(a + b) - c \\ d = 2(a + 2b + c) \end{cases},$$

from which the final form of the MR stored energy density reads

$$W(I_1, I_2, I_3) = a(I_1 - 3) + b(I_2 - 3) + c(I_3 - 1) - (a + 2b + c) \log(I_3). \quad (19)$$

From (19), the derivatives of W required for the computation of the stress component and bending moment given in the previous Sections assume the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{,1} &= a, & W_{,2} &= b, & W_{,3} &= c - \frac{r^4 R_0^2 e^{\frac{6Y}{r}} (a + 2b + c)}{r_0^4 \left[(r + R) e^{\frac{Y}{r}} - r_0 \cos \beta \right]^2}, \\ W_{,11} &= W_{,13} = W_{,12} = W_{,22} = W_{,23} = 0, \\ W_{,33} &= \frac{r^8 R_0^4 e^{\frac{8Y}{r}} (a + 2b + c)}{r_0^8 \left(r + R - r_0 e^{-\frac{Y}{r}} \cos \beta \right)^4}, \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

4.2. Mechanics of the bending model of solids

The derivatives (20) of the stored energy allow to obtain the principal components of the Biot stress tensor (4) and (5) for a MR material as

$$T_{B_1}(X, Y) = \frac{2r}{r_O} e^{\frac{Y}{r}} \left\{ a \left(\frac{r_O^2 e^{-\frac{2Y}{r}}}{r^2} - 1 \right) + b \left(\frac{r_O^4 e^{-\frac{4Y}{r}}}{r^4} - 2 \right) - c + \frac{r_O^2 e^{-\frac{6Y}{r}} \left(b r^2 e^{\frac{2Y}{r}} + c r_O^2 \right) \left[(r+R)e^{\frac{Y}{r}} - r_O \cos \beta \right]^2}{r^4 R_0^2} \right\}, \quad (21)$$

$$T_{B_3}(X, Y) = \frac{2R_0(a+2b+c)}{e^{-\frac{Y}{r}} r_O \cos \beta - r - R} + \frac{2}{R_0} \left[R + r - r_O e^{-\frac{Y}{r}} \cos \beta \right] \times \left[a + \frac{r_O^2 e^{-\frac{4Y}{r}} \left(2b r^2 e^{\frac{2Y}{r}} + c r_O^2 \right)}{r^4} \right]. \quad (22)$$

The nonlinear system of three equations for the solution of the problem can be achieved by introducing (21) and (22) into eqns.(6) and (8), namely

$$\begin{cases} R_0^2(2a+5b+c) + R[R(b+3c) - 2r(b+c)] = 0 \\ R_0 - R = r(1 - \cos \beta_0) \\ \int_A T_{B_3}(X, Y) dA = 0 \end{cases}. \quad (23)$$

Finally, numerical solution of system (23) provides the kinematic unknowns QN , r , and R .

Let us remark some aspects about system (23). Based on the ratio between the longitudinal and transversal radii of curvature [44], eq.(23)₁ can be interpreted as the *nonlinear Poisson ratio* for a MR material, namely

$$\nu_{MR} = \frac{2c + 2(a+3b+c)\frac{R_0^2}{R^2}}{(c-a) + (a+2b+c)\frac{R_0^2}{R^2}}, \quad (24)$$

that varies with the deformation. Moreover, eq.(8) admits the following two solutions:

$$r(1 - \cos \beta_0) + R = \pm R_0. \quad (25)$$

However, the left hand side of eq.(25) is always positive. Therefore, the only admissible solution of (8) is eq.(23)₂. As a consequence, the following inequality

holds true:

$$R_0 > R. \quad (26)$$

Relation (26) means that longitudinal neutral fiber M' lies above the transversal neutral fiber N' , as sketched in Figure 2. Finally, despite its unmanageable form, expression (23)₃ can be easily computed using a symbolical manipulator.

The moment-curvature relation is then obtained by substituting into (16) relation (20), thus providing

$$m_x(R_0) = \frac{4}{r^2 R_0} \int_0^{\beta_0} \int_{r_{\text{Min}}}^{r_{\text{Max}}} \frac{\rho(r+R-R_0-\rho \cos \beta)(\rho \cos \beta - 2r - R + r_0)}{\rho^2 \sin^2 \beta + (\rho \cos \beta - 3r - 2R + r_0)^2} \times \\ \left\{ a r^4 + [\rho^2 \sin^2 \beta + (\rho \cos \beta - r + r_0)^2] \left\{ 2 b r^2 + [\rho^2 \sin^2 \beta + (\rho \cos \beta - r + r_0)^2] \times \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left[c - \frac{r^4 R_0^2 (a + 2b + c)}{[\rho^2 + 2\rho \cos \beta (r_0 - r) + (r - r_0)^2]^2 (\rho \cos \beta - 2r - R + r_0)^2} \right] \right\} \right\} d\rho d\beta. \quad (27)$$

4.3. Approximations of the bending theory of solids

The linearisation of the present model allows us to introduce two different approximations of the modelling of bending: the *nonlinear Euler Elastica* (NEE) and the well known *Euler Elastica* (EE). Both the approximated formulations are achieved by imposing in the present model the condition $QN = 0$ which, in turn, implies $R_0 = R$ and $QM = 0$. In addition, linearisation of stretches and displacements is performed with respect to the dimensionless variables X/r and Y/r by expanding them in Taylor series and truncating the obtained expressions up to $o(X/r)^2$ and $o(Y/r)^2$.

The difference between EE and NEE formulation stands in the constitutive law. Starting from the present formulation, the EE theory is retrieved by linearising the principal stretches (1) and (2), thus obtaining the principal stress T_{B_3} based on a linear constitutive law. This corresponds to the linearisation of T_{B_3} , namely by truncating series expansion of eq.(22) up to $o(X/r)^2$ and $o(Y/r)^2$. Conversely, the NEE formulation is obtained with the same aforementioned linearisation of the stretches but assuming the nonlinear stress component T_{B_3} consistently with respect the constitutive law (3).

The investigation of the equilibrium conditions (23) for the linearised cases of EE and NEE allows to explain the limitation of the approximated theories. For both EE and NEE formulations, the assumption of $R_0 = R$ transforms eq.(23)₁ into the following relation:

$$r = \frac{a + 3b + 2c}{b + c}R. \quad (28)$$

Thus, relation (28) reduces the kinematic unknowns to the sole radius of curvature R , which becomes the control kinematic parameter of the problem. Similarly to (24), eq.(28) defines the *linearised Poisson ratio* for a compressible MR material as

$$\nu_{\text{MR}} = \frac{b + c}{a + 3b + 2c}. \quad (29)$$

Moreover, as shown in [1, 43] and in the following, the linearization of the constitutive law leads to the *linearised Young modulus* of a MR material

$$E_{\text{MR}} = \frac{4(a + b)(a + 4b + 3c)}{a + 3b + 2c}. \quad (30)$$

Combination of eqns.(29) and (30) gives the *linearised Lamé constants* of a compressible MR material as⁹

$$\mu_{\text{MR}} = 2(a + b), \quad \lambda_{\text{MR}} = 4(b + c). \quad (31)$$

Due to assumption $R_0 = R$, eq.(23)₂ is fulfilled. For both the EE and NEE theories, eq.(23)₃ will be discussed in the following based on the approximated forms of the stress component T_{B_3} of (22).

4.3.1. Nonlinear Euler Elastica (NEE)

By expanding in power series the principal stretches (1) and (2) one has

$$\lambda = 1 - \frac{Y}{R}\nu_{\text{MR}}, \quad \lambda_3 = 1 + \frac{Y}{R}. \quad (32)$$

⁹Note that the *linearised Shear modulus* (31)₁ is consistent with the well known formula $\mu = 2(W_{,1} + W_{,2})$ [45].

Accordingly with 32, evaluating the deformation invariants I_i , the deformation gradient \mathbf{F} , and the right Cauchy deformation tensor \mathbf{B} provides the expression of the stress component T_{B_3} as

$$T_{B_3} = 2 \left(\frac{Y}{R} + 1 \right) \left\{ a + \left(1 - \frac{Y}{R} \nu_{\text{MR}} \right)^2 \left[2b + c \left(1 - \frac{Y}{R} \nu_{\text{MR}} \right)^2 \right] \right\} + \frac{\lambda_{\text{MR}} R (\nu_{\text{MR}} - 1)}{2\nu_{\text{MR}} (R + Y)}. \quad (33)$$

The stress component (33) allows to compute the nonlinear bending moment according to the NEE theory as

$$m_{\text{NEE}}(R) = B \left\{ \frac{H^5 \nu_{\text{MR}}^2}{20R^3} [b + c(3 - 2\nu_{\text{MR}})] + \frac{cH^7 \nu_{\text{MR}}^4}{224R^5} - \frac{\lambda_{\text{MR}}}{2\nu_{\text{MR}}} \left[\frac{H^3}{3R} \left(\frac{\nu_{\text{MR}} - 1}{4} + \nu_{\text{MR}}^2 \right) + (\nu_{\text{MR}} - 1)R^2 \log \left(\frac{2R - H}{H + 2R} \right) + H(\nu_{\text{MR}} - 1)R \right] \right\}. \quad (34)$$

4.3.2. Euler Elastica (EE)

The *Euler Elastica* is achieved starting from the linearised principal stretches (32) and then introducing the linear constitutive law¹⁰ for an isotropic material. The resulting longitudinal stress component T_{B_3} corresponds to the linearisation of the stress component (22), namely

$$T_{B_3} = \frac{Y}{R} E_{\text{MR}}, \quad (35)$$

where E_{MR} is given by relation (30). Eq.(35) complies with the Bernoulli-Navier linearised stress-strain relation. Accordingly, the moment-curvature relation (13) provided by the EE formulation gives the well known formula

$$m_{\text{EE}}(R) = \frac{E_{\text{MR}} J_X}{R}, \quad (36)$$

being J_X the moment of inertia of the rectangular cross section. The results provided by the above formulations will be compared in Section 6 with respect to results of finite element simulations.

¹⁰The linearisation of the constitutive law leads to a number of analytical paradoxes [46, 47] as the violation of principle of material indifference.

5. Finite element model

The finite element (FE) model used to compare the predictions of the theoretical model described within the previous Section to numerical results is described in the current section.

The numerical simulations have been carried out with the finite element code COMSOL Multiphysics[®] v.5.6. Because of symmetry conditions, only one fourth of the solid have been modelled, see Figure 5. A user defined material

Figure 5: Reference and deformed configurations of the FE model: in evidence the restraints, rigid connector and its centre of rotation.

has been associated to the solid. Such a material allows the implementation of the stored energy density (19) as a function of the principal stretches of the solid.

Meshes are created using hexagonal brick elements characterized by a quality ratio of 0.99. The meshes are realized by dividing the minimum side of the block into 20 elements. Cubic serendipity shape functions have been used.

In terms of restraints, displacement components normal to each plane of symmetry are neglected, see blue and red surfaces of Figure 5. The bending is imparted by using flexible rigid connectors. The flexible rigid connector is

applied to the final cross section of the solid and it allows in-plane deformations, see green surfaces of Figure 5. This feature is associated to a moving centre of rotation that lies on an axis parallel to X direction. In addition, Y component of the displacement of the centre of rotation is neglected. The rotation α_0 is thus applied to the cross section by the rigid connector. Thus, a static incremental analysis is performed by increasing the values of the prescribed rotation.

The Eulerian bending moment provided by the FE model is obtained by the following strategy: the deformed cross section at $Z = 0$ is partitioned in a number of elements of area A'_i ; Cauchy stress tensor component T_{3i} at the centroid of each element A'_i is assessed; distances \hat{y}_i of each centroid of elements A'_i from the neutral line for which $\lambda_3(x, y, 0) = 1$ are extracted; finally, the bending moment is assessed as

$$m_{\text{FE}}(R_0) = \sum_{k=1}^K \hat{y}_k T_{3k} A'_k, \quad (37)$$

being K the number of surface elements used for the discretization of the deformed cross section.

6. Results and discussion

In the present section comparisons between theoretical predictions and numerical results based on FE simulations are provided in terms of non-vanishing axial force, distribution of stretches and stresses over the cross sections and moment-curvature relationship.

For sake of definiteness, the constitutive parameters of a MR material in agreement with [48] are $a = 456.9$, $b = 381.1$ and $c = 317.6$ kPa. The geometries of the solid are chosen by fixing $B = 20$ mm and the ratio $L = 600$ mm. Only the height of the solid will be changed, thus introducing different investigated cases.

Three different cases are considered, as shown in Figure 6. Case (I) is characterized by a compactness index [49] $\beta_C = B/H = 4$ and it resembles a slender

Figure 6: Reference and deformed configurations of the FE models for the investigated cases for $\alpha_0 = 180^\circ$: (a) case (I): $H = B/4$; Case (II): $H = B$; Case (III): $H = 4B$. For each case it is $B = 20$ mm and $L = 600$ mm. Contour plots are referred to the norm of the displacement vector.

slab slender solid. Case (II) is has a compactness index $\beta_C = 1$ and it denotes a slender beam with compact cross section. Case (III) is characterized by $\beta_C = 1/4$ and it represents a squat solid similar to a wall beam element.

Comparison is performed among results provided by FE simulations and three theoretical models: present theory of bending of solids (S); nonlinear Euler *Elastica* (NEE) formulation of Section 4.3.1; Euler *Elastica* (EE) formulation of Section 4.3.2. Although a FE solution is not an exact solution, in the following it is assumed as reference solution. Accordingly, given a field f , the relative error affecting the theoretical model is here defined as $\varepsilon_{r,f} = 1 - f_{Th}/f_{FEM}$, being f_{Th} and f_{FEM} the values provided by FE and theoretical solutions for that field, respectively.

Figure 7 shows the axial force N (defined in eq. (9)) normalized with respect to $E_{MR}A$. Such a normalization, i.e. $N/E_{MR}A$, resembles a measure of the the axial deformation induced by an axial force N . The results provided by the *Elastica* are omitted in Figure 7 since it gives a vanishing axial force.

Both the present model S and the FE simulations provide vanishing or negligible normalised axial forces as depicted in Figs.7. This is ensured by equilibrium condition (9) for the model S and by the regime of almost pure bending simulated by the FE model.

The red curves in Figure 7, denote the results provided by the NEE for-

Figure 7: Normalised axial force (N) as a function of the curvature $\chi_0 = 1/R_0$ in case of bending model for solids (S), nonlinear Euler *Elastica* (NEE), and finite element (FE): (a) case (I) with $H = B/4$; case (II) with $H = B$; case (III) with $H = 4B$. For each case it has been assumed $B = 20$ mm and $L = 600$ mm.

mulation. It is shown that they give a residual axial force, which grows as the curvature increases owing to the approximations. For a fixed value of the curvature $\chi_0 = 1/R_0$, the errors of NEE formulation increase from case (I) (Figure 7(a)) to case (III) (Figure 7(c)) due to the decreasing of the *Eulerian slenderness* $\beta_{ES} = R_0/H$ [49]. Indeed, by introducing relation (33) into (9), the normalised axial force provided by the NEE theory turns out to be

$$\frac{N}{E_{MR}A} = -\beta_{ES}^{-2} \left\{ \frac{1}{1 - 2\nu_{MR}^2 - \nu_{MR}} \left[\frac{1}{24} + \nu_{MR}^2 \left(\frac{1}{8} - \frac{\nu_{MR}}{3} \right) \right] - \frac{2b\nu_{MR}^2}{3E_{MR}} \right\}. \quad (38)$$

Eq.(38) clearly shows that the normalised axial force, closer to an axial strain measure, increases as the Eulerian slenderness decreases. Recalling the bounds of the linearised Poisson ratio, $0 \leq \nu_{MR} \leq 0.5$, it follows that eq.(38) turns out to be always negative. This circumstance reveals an excess of compressive axial force. This unbalanced state of stress is generated by the approximations lying in the NEE formulation due to the impossibility to fulfil vanishing of the resultant of the longitudinal stress, i.e. eq.(9).

Figure 8 shows the longitudinal principal stretch $\lambda_3(0, Y)$ for five values of prescribed rotation α_0 of the final cross sections of the solid. Excepted for case (III) reported in Figure 8(c), for low values of α_0 all formulations predict the same distribution of the principal stretch λ_3 through-the-thickness of the solid that are almost linear. It is remarked that only the stretch profiles provided by the EE solution are exactly linear.

Figure 8: Comparison in terms of longitudinal principal stretch $\lambda_3(0, Y)$ for $\alpha_0 = \{15^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ, 120^\circ, 180^\circ\}$ provided by the model (S), the Euler *Elastica* (EE), nonlinear Euler Elastica (NEE), and FE simulation: (a) case (I) with $H = B/4$; case (II) with $H = B$; case (III) with $H = 4B$. For each cases $B = 20$ mm and $L = 600$ mm.

Despite of the similarity in terms of stretch distributions shown in Figs. 8(a) and 8(b), relevant differences arise among cases (I) and (II). The coordinate $Y = -QM$ of eq.(B.1), i.e. the position of the unstretched longitudinal fiber, increase its value as the deformation increases moving toward the negative Y , as clearly shown in Figure B.13(a). While for cases (I) and (II) the value of QM can be considered negligible, in the case (III) QM reaches values close to $0.08 H$ when $\alpha_0 = 180^\circ$. Thereby, in case of non-slender solid the kinematic must be capable to grasp the motion of the unstretched fiber.

The stress distributions of the investigated cases are reported in Figure 9. For case (I), as for the stretches distribution of Figure 8(a), also the stress profiles of Figure 9(a) maintain a quasi-linear behaviour for each proposed solution. The capability to accurately predict the stress of the EE and NEE models slightly gets worse for case (II) of Figure 9(b). For the investigated prescribed angles, EE and NEE are able to predict the distributions of stretches and stresses for case (I) and (II).

For case (III), significant errors affect both the EE and NEE formulations, as shown in Figure 9(c). As expected, these errors increase as the prescribed rotation increases, making such approximated formulations unable to grasp the flexural behaviour of squat solids. Figs.3, 7(c), 8(c), and 9(c) put in light the limitations of EE and NEE approaches. EE dramatically fails in the description

Figure 9: Comparison in terms of longitudinal component of the Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor $[\mathbf{T}_R]_{33}$ at $X = Z = 0$ within the height of the solid for $\alpha_0 = \{15^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ, 120^\circ, 180^\circ\}$ provided by model (S), the Euler *Elastica* (EE), nonlinear Euler *Elastica* (NEE), and FE simulation: (a) case (I) with $H = B/4$; case (II) with $H = B$; case with (III) $H = 4B$. For each cases $B = 20$ mm and $L = 600$ mm; (d) uniaxial stress-stretch curve of compressible MR material (s vs λ_3 from [43]).

of the stress distribution owing to the approximations affecting both the kinematics and constitutive behaviour of the material. On the other hand, when deformation increases also NEE fails, thus showing that the assumption of a nonlinear constitutive law is not sufficient to provide accurate predictions.

The unreliability of both the EE and NEE formulations to grasp stresses and stresses could also be observed for slender solids when high values of curvature are reached. The reliability of EE and NEE does not depend only on the geometric aspect ratio of the solid. It will be shown in the following that, for a fixed set of constitutive parameters, the reliability of such formulations depends on the Eulerian slenderness β_{ES} also.

Results in terms of moment-curvature relation and the associated relative errors ε_r with respect to the FE solution up to $\alpha_0 = 210^\circ$ are reported in

Figure 10. If the height of the cross section is much lower than its length

Figure 10: Moment-curvature relations (on left) obtained with model for solid S (black lines), Euler *Elastica* (red lines), nonlinear Euler *Elastica* (red dashed lines), FE model (blue lines), and relative errors (on the right) computed with respect to FE results: (a) case (I) with $H = B/4$; case (II) with $H = B$; case with (III) $H = 4B$. For each case it is $B = 20$ mm and $L = 600$ mm.

(slender solids), the moment-curvature relation provides a nearly linear trend for each approach. This happens for cases (I) and (II) as shown in Figs.10(a) and 10(b). Note that the EE formulation provides a perfectly linear moment-curvature relation (see eq.(36)) regardless of the size of the cross section. Despite the nonlinearity of the moment-curvature relations involved in the S, NEE and FE models, an almost linear behaviour is found as a consequence of the quasi-linear distribution of the stress depicted in Figs.9(a) and 9(b). Indeed, when the compactness index $\beta_C < 1$ and the Eulerian slenderness β_{ES} is large, as it occurs for cases (I) and (II), both the kinematic and constitutive nonlinearities do not produce relevant effects. For cases (I) and (II), in the investigated range of curvature, all the obtained solutions are similar and they are able to grasp the mechanical response of the system. Indeed, the associated relative errors shown in Figs.10(a) and 10(b) are negligible, $\varepsilon_r < 1\%$. Conversely, if the height of the solid is comparable with the length, the moment-curvature relations clearly show a nonlinear trend for large deformations. It is noteworthy that case (III) exhibits different behaviours in terms of moment-curvature response, as shown in Figure 10(c), in which a softening branch is observed in the solutions provided by S and FE models. On the other hand, the behaviour of the NEE solution shown in Figure 10(c) highlights a slightly hardening response. Indeed, the stress profile in Figure 9(c) of case (III) is characterised by an excess of compression that generates a hardening response in terms of moment-curvature law. However, this behaviour is not effective and it differs from both the FE and S predictions.

As the deformation increases, both the EE and NEE formulations lead to important errors, close to 20%, as shown in Figure 10(c). However, the important errors affecting case (III) can also be found in cases (I) and (II) if the Eulerian slenderness decreases. To show that, let's introduce the dimensionless bending moment $\bar{m} = m_S/E_{MR}BH^2$ [49] (such a normalization reduces the dimensionless bending moment provided by the EE formulation (36) to $\bar{m} = \beta_{ES}^{-1}$).

The dimensionless bending moments of the investigated cases are reported in Figure 11 varying the inverse of the Eulerian slenderness β_{ES} . Such a plot highlights the fact that EE formulation is reliable when low values of β_{ES}^{-1} take

Figure 11: Nonlinear effects related to the Eulerian slenderness: (a) dimensionless bending moment as a function of the inverse of the Eulerian slenderness; (b) longitudinal component of the Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor $[\mathbf{T}_R]_{33}$ at $X = Z = 0$ along the height of the cross section for $\alpha_0 = 720^\circ$ ($\beta_{ES}^{-1} = 0.837$) provided by the model of the solid (S), the Euler *Elastica* (EE), the nonlinear Euler *Elastica* (NEE), and FE model for case (II) with $H = B$.

place, i.e. when small deformations and linear constitutive law apply. Each investigated case lies on the same curve of Figure 11. The only difference among cases (I), (II) and (III) is the values of β_{ES}^{-1} at which that curves are interrupted, which correspond to $\alpha_0 = 210^\circ$.

In Figure 11 points corresponding to $\alpha_0 = 210^\circ$ are denoted with $P_{(I)}$, $P_{(II)}$ and $P_{(III)}$ for cases (I), (II) and (III), respectively. For case (II) (high lagrangian slenderness and compact cross section) and for $\beta_{ES}^{-1} = 0.9$, both the EE and NEE models lead to significant errors in terms of stretches and stresses, as already shown in Figs.8(c) and 9(c). In detail, Figure 11(b) shows the comparison in terms of stress distribution for case (II) for $\beta_{ES}^{-1} = 0.837$, corresponding to $\alpha_0 = 720^\circ$. Note that this situation for case (II) gives the same Eulerian slenderness of case (III) at $\alpha_0 = 180^\circ$. Indeed, as reported by Figure 11(b), the stress exhibits the same behaviour of Figure 9(c) for $\alpha_0 = 180^\circ$. This confirms that the Eulerian slenderness governs the problem of bending.

Once the constitutive parameter are fixed, the \bar{m} vs β_{ES}^{-1} curve describes the behaviour of any solid under pure bending obeying to the MR constitutive law. Except instability phenomena, curve of Figure 11 always holds true provided that $\beta_C = B/H$ takes low values, such to avoid "plate effects".

In [49] about the bending theory of slender beams, it was already pointed

out that there were limits in terms of β_{ES}^{-1} and β_{C} for which that model loses its accuracy. For that model the limits was found in [49] corresponding to $\beta_{\text{C}} < 0.5$ and $\beta_{\text{ES}}^{-1} < 0.125$. Those limits are drastically relaxed by the present formulation. In particular, for the present theory of bent solids, $\beta_{\text{C}} \leq 1/4$ and $\beta_{\text{ES}}^{-1} \leq 1$ ensure relative errors affecting stretches, stresses and bending moment lower than 5%, 6%, and 2%, respectively.

The gap between the nonlinear trend exhibited by case (III) and the linear trend provided by the *Elastica* in Figure 11, depicted with a grey area, highlights the onset of a nonlinear (geometrical and constitutive) behaviour that takes relevance as the deformation increases. The growth of this area puts in light the limitations of the EE theory. For the parameters of the MR material here considered, the limit can be fixed at $\beta_{\text{ES}}^{-1} < 0.5$, corresponding to a relative error in terms of bending moment equal to $\varepsilon_r = 5\%$.

7. Conclusions

The problem of finite bending of solids made of hyperelastic materials [1] has been improved in the present work by considering also the equilibrium condition in terms of resultant of the normal stresses over the cross sections. The relevance of the corresponding new equation has been discussed, showing that it is fundamental to accurately predict stretches and stresses. Correspondingly, a new moment-curvature relationship for bent solids has been found.

The linearisation of the present model for solids has led to two kinds of approximation. The first one, the Euler *Elastica* (EE) formulation, has been obtained as the leading order term of the series expansion of the kinematics of the present model together with the assumption of a linear constitutive law. Conversely, the linearisation of the kinematics together with the assumption of a nonlinear constitutive law has led to the nonlinear Euler *Elastica* (NEE) formulation.

The present model and its approximations have been compared with FE simulations. Comparisons on three investigated cases, characterised by solids

with different height of the cross section, have been carried out. Relevant errors affecting stretch and stress distributions within the height of the solid cross section have been found for case (III) by using the approximated theories. This is due to the fact that, conversely to cases (I) and (II) in which the solids are extremely slender, in case (III) the solid is characterized by an aspect ratio $B = H/4 = 7.5L$, which denotes an extremely squat solid. For such a case, the Eulerian slenderness $\beta_{ES} = R_0/H$ increases faster than the other cases. Based on the dimensionless form of the moment-curvature relationship (\bar{m} vs β_{ES}^{-1}) here proposed, it has been shown how the approximations involved into the *Elastica* formulations can lead to relevant errors also in case of slender solids.

For fixed values of the constitutive parameters of the Mooney-Rivlin material, the \bar{m} vs β_{ES}^{-1} relation summarizes the bending behaviour of any solid. It has been found that when (geometrical and/or constitutive) nonlinearities take relevance, the \bar{m} vs β_{ES}^{-1} curves exhibit softening.

The limits of the present bending theory of solid can be expressed as $\beta_C = B/H \leq 1/4$ and $\beta_{ES}^{-1} \leq 1$. These limits are such to ensure relative errors (with respect FE predictions) in terms of stretches, stresses and bending moment lower than 5%, 6%, and 2%, respectively. Under this limits, the relation \bar{m} vs β_{ES}^{-1} is independent from the geometries of the solid but, conversely to the Euler *Elastica* formulation, it is able to predict the nonlinearities in case of large bending. The more the \bar{m} vs β_{ES}^{-1} curve differs from linear behavior the more the Elastic Euler formulation fails in the prediction of stretches, stresses, and bending moment.

The curve \bar{m} vs β_{ES}^{-1} allows highlighting the limitations of the *Elastica* theory to properly predict the behaviour of prismatic solids under bending.

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Appendix A. Relevant kinematic and stress quantities

For convenience, both the main kinematic and stress amounts needed to obtain the relevant expressions reported in the previous Sections are listed in Tables A.1 and A.2.

Appendix B. Relevant loci of the bending model for solids

Four different fundamental neutral loci are considered in the present theory for bending of solids. Each of these geometric loci can be expressed in the reference as well as in the deformed configuration. Neutral loci can be referred to kinematic or mechanical aspects, unstretched or unstressed fibres, respectively. Moreover, neutral loci are associated to longitudinal direction, λ_3 and T_{R_3} , and transversal direction λ and T_{R_1} .

In the reference configuration, the transverse principal stretch λ and longitudinal principal stretch λ_3 are given in eqns.(1) and (2), respectively. The principal stretch λ assumes unitary value at the transverse neutral fibers $N = (0, -QN, Z)$, while the principal stretch λ_3 is unitary at the longitudinal neutral fibers $M = (0, -QM, Z)$.

The coordinate QN represents a kinematic unknown of the problem. Conversely, QM is obtained as a function of the three kinematic unknowns of the problem by imposing the unitary value of eq.(12), namely

$$QM = QN + r \log \left(1 + \frac{R - R_0}{r} \right). \quad (\text{B.1})$$

Note that for a MR material (19), eq.(B.1) compared with the constrain $R_0 > R$ given in eq.(26) leads to

$$QN \geq QM \geq 0 \quad (\text{B.2})$$

As a consequence of the kinematic assumptions, in the deformed configuration the unstretched fibers N and M became arcs of circumference characterised

Kinematics	
Displacement vector, $\mathbf{sp}(P)$	$\begin{aligned} & \tan \beta (r + R - R_0 \lambda_3) - X \\ & \cos \alpha R_0 \lambda_3 - (R + r - r_0) - Y \\ & \sin \alpha R_0 \lambda_3 - Z \end{aligned}$
Deformation vector, $\boldsymbol{\varphi}(P)$	$\begin{bmatrix} r_0 e^{-\frac{Y}{r}} \sin \beta \\ r_0 - (r + R) + \left(r + R - r_0 e^{-\frac{Y}{r}} \cos \beta \right) \cos \alpha \\ \left(r + R - r_0 e^{-\frac{Y}{r}} \cos \beta \right) \sin \alpha \end{bmatrix}$
Transverse (minor) principal stretch, $\lambda(P)$ and $\lambda(P')$	$r_0 e^{-\frac{Y}{r}} / r$ $\sqrt{\frac{x^2 + \left[r + R - \sqrt{(r + R - r_0 + y)^2 + z^2} \right]^2}{r^2}}$
Longitudinal (major) principal stretch, $\lambda_3(P)$ and $\lambda_3(P')$	$\left(R + r - r_0 e^{-\frac{Y}{r}} \cos \beta \right) / R_0$ $\sqrt{\frac{(r + R - r_0 + y)^2 + z^2}{R_0^2}}$
Right Cauchy deformation tensor, \mathbf{C}	$\begin{bmatrix} \lambda^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda_3^2 \end{bmatrix}$
Left Cauchy deformation tensor, \mathbf{B}	$\begin{bmatrix} \lambda^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda^2 \cos^2 \alpha + \lambda_3^2 \sin^2 \alpha & \frac{1}{2} \sin 2\alpha (\lambda - \lambda_3)^2 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} \sin 2\alpha (\lambda - \lambda_3)^2 & \lambda^2 \sin^2 \alpha + \lambda_3^2 \cos^2 \alpha \end{bmatrix}$
Rotation of XY planes around X , $\alpha(P)$ and $\alpha(P')$	Z / R_0 $\text{atan} \left(\frac{z}{R + y + r - r_0} \right)$
Rotation of ZY planes around Z , $\beta(P)$ and $\beta(P')$	X / r $\text{atan} \left[\frac{x}{R + r - \sqrt{z^2 + (R + y + r - r_0)^2}} \right]$
Characteristic transversal radii of curvature,	$r_0 = r(X, 0, Z) = r e^{-\frac{QN}{r}},$ $r_{\min} = r(X, H/2, Z) = r e^{-\frac{H+2QN}{2r}},$ $r_{\max} = r(X, -H/2, Z) = r e^{\frac{H-2QN}{2r}}$
Mapping from Lagrangian to Eulerian coordinates	$\begin{cases} X = -r \beta(P') \\ Y = -r \log \{ x \csc [\beta(P')] / r \} - QN \\ Z = R_0 \alpha(P') \end{cases}$

Table A.1: Kinematics of the bending model for solids.

Mechanics	
First Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor, \mathbf{T}_R	$\begin{bmatrix} T_{B_1} \cos \beta & -T_{B_1} \sin \beta & 0 \\ T_{B_1} \cos \alpha \sin \beta & T_{B_1} \cos \alpha \cos \beta & -T_{B_3} \sin \alpha \\ T_{B_1} \sin \alpha \sin \beta & T_{B_1} \cos \beta \sin \alpha & T_{B_3} \cos \alpha \end{bmatrix}$
Biot stress tensor, \mathbf{T}_B	$\begin{bmatrix} T_{B_1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & T_{B_1} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & T_{B_3} \end{bmatrix}$
Cauchy stress tensor in the principal reference system, \mathbf{T}	$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{T_{B_1}}{\lambda\lambda_3} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{T_{B_1}}{\lambda\lambda_3} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{T_{B_3}}{\lambda^2} \end{bmatrix}$

Table A.2: Mechanics of the bending model for solid.

by the longitudinal radii of curvature R and R_0 , see Figure 2. Indeed, the Eulerian principal stretches assume unitary value at the following characteristic neutral fibers:

$$\begin{aligned} N' &\equiv \left(0, r_O - r - R + \sqrt{R^2 - z^2}, z\right) : \lambda(N') = 1 \\ M' &\equiv \left(0, r_O - r - R + \sqrt{R_0^2 - z^2}, z\right) : \lambda_3(M') = 1 \end{aligned} \quad . \quad (\text{B.3})$$

In terms of kinematics in the reference configuration, the neutral lines \mathcal{NL} shown in Figure B.12 assume the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{NL}_\lambda &\equiv (X, -QN, 0) : \lambda(\mathcal{NL}_\lambda) = 1 \\ \mathcal{NL}_{\lambda_3} &\equiv (X, -QM + r \log(\cos X/r), 0) : \lambda_3(\mathcal{NL}_{\lambda_3}) = 1 \end{aligned} \quad . \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Eqns.(B.4) shown that transverse neutral line \mathcal{NL}_λ is a straight line parallel to the X axis in the Lagrangian configuration, as shown in Figure B.12. Conversely, Lagrangian longitudinal neutral line \mathcal{NL}_{λ_3} varies with the X coordinate assuming a negative concavity.

As a consequence of the longitudinal bending, in the deformed configuration the transversal neutral line \mathcal{NL}'_λ assumes a positive concavity, whilst the longitudinal neutral line $\mathcal{NL}'_{\lambda_3}$ becomes a straight line parallel to the X axis, as shown in Figure B.12. This behaviour can be easily proofed recalling eqns.(11)

Figure B.12: Kinematic neutral fibers and principal stretch distributions at $X = z = 0$: (a) lagrangian quantities; (b) Eulerian quantities.

and (12), from which the neutral lines in the deformed configuration read

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{NL}'_{\lambda} &\equiv \left(x, r_0 - \sqrt{r^2 - x^2}, 0\right) : \lambda(\mathcal{NL}'_{\lambda}) = 1 \\ \mathcal{NL}'_{\lambda_3} &\equiv \left(x, r_0 - r + R_0 - R, 0\right) : \lambda_3(\mathcal{NL}'_{\lambda_3}) = 1 \end{aligned} \quad . \quad (\text{B.5})$$

As shown by relations (B.5), transversal neutral line \mathcal{NL}'_{λ} is an arc of circumference centred at $(x = 0, y = r_0)$ of radius r whilst longitudinal neutral line $\mathcal{NL}'_{\lambda_3}$ is a straight segment.

The distribution of the 3D neutral loci are here named neutral planes \mathcal{NP} . These loci in reference configuration are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{NP}_{\lambda} &\equiv \left(X, -QN, Z\right) : \lambda(\mathcal{NP}_{\lambda}) = 1 \\ \mathcal{NP}_{\lambda_3} &\equiv \left(X, -QM + r \log(\cos X/r), Z\right) : \lambda_3(\mathcal{NP}_{\lambda_3}) = 1 \end{aligned} \quad , \quad (\text{B.6})$$

Transverse neutral plane \mathcal{NP}_{λ} is a plane parallel to the XZ plane belonging to the coordinate $Y = -QN$. Otherwise, the longitudinal neutral plane \mathcal{NP}_{λ_3} is a surface characterized by a negative concavity ($\cos X/r < 1$), Figure B.12.

Based on the mapping between Lagrangian and Eulerian coordinates listed in Table A.1, the neutral planes (B.6) in the deformed configuration turn out

to be

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{N}\mathcal{P}'_\lambda &\equiv \left(x, \sqrt{r^2 + (r+R)^2 - x^2 - z^2 + 2(r+R)\sqrt{r^2 - x^2} + r_O - r - R}, z \right) : \lambda(\mathcal{N}\mathcal{P}'_\lambda) = 1, \\ \mathcal{N}\mathcal{P}'_{\lambda_3} &\equiv \left(x, \sqrt{R_0^2 - z^2 + r_O - r - R}, z \right) : \lambda_3(\mathcal{N}\mathcal{P}'_{\lambda_3}) = 1.\end{aligned}\tag{B.7}$$

In relation (B.7)₁, the transverse neutral plane $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{P}'_\lambda$ represents the equation of the *anticlastic surface* characterised by a saddle-like shape. Differently, the longitudinal neutral plane $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{P}'_{\lambda_3}$ is a portion of a cylinder with generating axis directed along the axis X and crossing the coordinate $(y = R_0 + r_O - (r + R), z = 0)$.

The neutral loci in terms of stresses are more complex with respect to those given in terms of stretches because of the dependence on the constitutive model. However, some consideration can be drawn regarding the longitudinal neutral loci of the mechanics in both reference and deformed configurations.

In the reference configuration, the Y coordinates associated to unstressed fiber is obtained by imposing the vanishing of relation (5). Roots of relation (5) provide the unstressed longitudinal neutral fiber $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{L}_{T_{B_3}}$ as follow:

$$Y = -QN + r \log \left(\frac{r \cos \beta}{r + R} \right), \quad Y = -QN + r \log \left(\pm \sqrt{-\frac{\sqrt{W_{,2}^2 - W_{,1}W_{,3}} \pm W_{,2}}{W_{,1}}} \right)\tag{B.8}$$

The numerical simulations of the present model of solids suggest that in case of MR material the only admissible root of (B.8) is

$$Y = -QN + \frac{r}{2} \log \left(\frac{W_{,2} - \sqrt{W_{,2}^2 - W_{,1}W_{,3}}}{W_{,1}} \right).\tag{B.9}$$

Therefore, the Lagrangian longitudinal neutral line of the mechanics can be given in the following implicit form:

$$\mathcal{N}\mathcal{L}_{T_{B_3}} \equiv (X, \check{Y}(X), 0) : T_{B_3}(\mathcal{N}\mathcal{L}_{T_{B_3}}) = 0,\tag{B.10}$$

in which $\check{Y}(X)$ represents a solution of the following nonlinear equation

$$\check{Y}(X) + QN = r \log \sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{W_{,2}^2 - W_{,1}W_{,3}} - W_{,2}}{W_{,1}}}.\tag{B.11}$$

In particular, for a MR material (19), the Lagrangian longitudinal neutral line (B.11) reads

$$\check{Y}_{\text{MR}}(X) + QN = \frac{r}{2} \log \left(\sqrt{\frac{r^4 R_0^2 e^{\frac{6\check{Y}_{\text{MR}}(X)}{r}} (a + 2b + c)}{ar_{\text{O}}^4 \left[r_{\text{O}} - (r + R) e^{\frac{\check{Y}_{\text{MR}}(X)}{r}} \right]^2} - \frac{c}{a} + \frac{b^2}{a^2} - \frac{b}{a}} \right) \quad (\text{B.12})$$

From (B.12) it follows that the longitudinal unstressed fiber shown in Figure B.13(a) for a MR material is assessed as

$$QM_R = \check{Y}_{\text{MR}}(0). \quad (\text{B.13})$$

The position of unstressed fiber (B.13) normalised with respect to the height of the solid is reported in Figure B.13(a) for the cases investigated in Section 6.

Figure B.13: Effect of the curvature on the geometrical loci: (a) position of the normalised neutral fiber varying the longitudinal curvature; (b) unstressed neutral fiber in the plane of the cross section at $\alpha_0 = 180^\circ$.

The figure shows that the Y coordinate of the unstressed fiber at $X = 0$ grows as the prescribed rotation α_0 increases. For case (III) the unstressed fiber plays an important role as its distance from the centroid assumes values close to 8% of the height of the cross section when the solid is bent on itself.

It is worth noticing that in case (I), for which $B = 4H = L$, the Y coordinate of the neutral fiber at $X = 0$ assumes positive values. However, for case (I), the distribution of the neutral fiber along the X axis changes its sign in the neighbourhood of $X = B/4$ as reported in Figure B.13. The variation of the neutral fiber along the width of the solid is much more relevant when $B > H$.

This highlights the arising of the "plate effects". Obviously, such a variation with respect to X cannot be observed by adopting plane strain regime [24, 25, 26, 4, 28].

The definition of Cauchy stress component T_3 , given in eq.(10), highlights the fact that the Eulerian unstressed longitudinal fiber corresponds to the Lagrangian unstressed longitudinal fiber. Thereby, such a fiber is assessed by using the Eulerian coordinate $y(0, QM_R, 0)$ given in Table A.1, thus leading to

$$QM'_R = r_O \left(1 - e^{-\frac{QM_R}{r}} \right).$$

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